
Revolutionary Virtue: Schiller and Freedom *from* Religion

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Abstract: The following study provides a view of the distinct freedom-*from*-religion metanarrative in Schiller's works. The titular distinction between freedom *of* religion and freedom *from* religion is intended to emphasize the prerequisites for unfettered exercise of freedom of thought and freedom of conscience; namely, not only the guarantee of freedom to associate with one of the state-approved religions, but the freedom to choose none of them and the guaranty of freedom from any state, church, majority, or minority coercion through religion. Schiller's regulative idea regarding religion was the rejection of faith and subject-external belief system ("no religion"). In texts dating back to as early as 1779, Schiller articulates the reasons why religion precludes the possibility of genuine virtue and civilization, and thus hinders the realization of a secular republican vision; he therefore rejects defenses of faith, organized religion, divine judgement, and belief in the afterlife.

Keywords: atheism, secularism, religiosity, allegory, church/state separation, virtue.

Uns braucht man nicht mehr
(They don't need us anymore)
— Church-State Intrigant, Domingo¹

As Friedrich Schiller (1759-1805) strongly suggests in "Mein Glaube" (1796) above, his regulative idea regarding religion was the rejection of faith and subject-external belief systems — "no religion": "Welche Religion ich bekenne? Keine von allen, / Die du mir nennst! 'Und warum keine?' Aus Religion" (NA 1:296). In texts dating back to as early as 1779, Schiller articulates the reasons why religion precludes the possibility of genuine virtue and civilization, and thus hinders the realization of the secular republican vision exemplified by Socrates' choice of death over church-state coercion in Schiller's first Karlschule speech, "Gehört allzuviel Güte, Leutseeligkeit und große Freygiebigkeit im engsten Verstande zur Tugend?" In "Ueber den moralischen Nutzen ästhetischer Sitten" (1793), Schiller distinguishes between the "zufällige Tugend" produced by religion — a surrogate for true virtue² — as a means toward temporary pseudo-civilization³ and the rule of reason as the end in itself (NA 21:37). Throughout his works and letters, Schiller rejects defenses of faith — "das Morsche Gebäude der Dummheit" (1793, NA 26:219), organized religion — "das künstlichste aller Gebäuden" (1795, NA 20:423) —

its method — "Verlängung der Wahrheit" (1795, NA 20:423). Logically, Schiller's works also constitute a consistent campaign against the belief in the afterlife — "Glauben an Unsterblichkeit" (1786, NA 20:122)⁴ and "Aussichten auf eine Unsterblichkeit" (1795, NA 21:37). Divine judgment is reduced to a mostly misunderstood metaphor for the evaluation of the history of human activity in "Resignation" (1786) — "Die Weltgeschichte ist das Weltgericht" (NA 1:168) — and portrayed as a projection of human judgment in "An die Freude" (1786) — "Richtet Gott wie wir gerichtet" (NA 1:171). In "An die Freude" (1786), joy itself is the creator and drives the otherwise indifferent mechanical clock ("Weltenuhr"; NA 1:170) that is the universe. Consequently, in 1799, charges of atheism against his University of Jena colleague Johann Gottlieb Fichte (1762-1814) elicit a telling response from Schiller in a letter of 26 January. Schiller demonstrates no interest in Fichte's atheism as a moral question; on the contrary, he encourages Fichte to defend his non-belief in a separate essay. Predictably, Schiller is interested in the unjust interference of a religious law that seeks to ban a theoretical discussion intended to enlighten readers, and encourages Fichte to seize the opportunity to defend freedom from religion:

Was meine besondere Meinung betrifft, so hätte ich allerdings gewünscht, dass Sie Ihr Glaubensbekenntniß über die Religion in einer besonderen Schrift ruhig und selbst ohne die geringste Empfindlichkeit gegen das Sächsische Consistorium abgelegt hätten. Dagegen hätte ich [...] bewiesen, dass das Verbot Ihrer Schrift, selbst wenn sie wirklich atheistisch wäre, noch immer unstatthaft bleibe; denn eine aufgeklärte und gerechte Regierung kann keine theoretische Meinung, welche in einem gelehrten Werke für Gelehrte dargelegt wird, verbieten. Hierin würden Ihnen Alle, auch die Philosophen von der Gegenparthei, beigetreten sein [...] (NA 30:26).

Religion appears consistently in Schiller's works as a system of coercive incentives invented by "schlaue Priester" (1780, NA 20:54) that not only hinders the progress of civilizations, but in fact poses a grave danger to "das kühnste Ideal einer Menschenrepublik," one based on guarantees of individual freedom from church-state and majority coercion and characterized by "allgemeiner Duldung und Gewissensfreiheit" (1787; NA 22:141). These positions find no serious contradiction in Schiller's writings after the last letters of his adolescence and Klopstockian odes in 1777, an influence Schiller distanced

himself from as an adult specifically due to its religious orientation.⁵ The following study provides a summary view of the distinct freedom-from-religion metanarrative in Schiller's works, one that embarks from Hermann Samuel Reimarus' (1694-1768) analysis of the widespread belief in the irrational as a case of mass failure to read allegorically that which was written allegorically, as articulated in *Fragmente eines Wolfenbüttelschen Ungenannten* (1774), edited by Lessing.⁶ It is precisely the common inability to read allegorically that allowed Schiller to defy ideological coercion and publish blasphemous positions by dialectically coopting and deconstructing religious imagery and subtly drawing attention to its earthly sources and concerns. It is likewise a failure (or unwillingness) to read allegorically that allows for the continued interpretation of Schiller's essentially secularist works as religious-morally informed, as opposed to moral-philosophically informed.

I.

The path to a clear view of the secularist Schiller has been obscured by a very large number of attempts to missionize Schiller posthumously.⁷ These commonly embark from anecdotal evidence, paraphrased here: *When Schiller was a child, he wanted to become a minister, one of the few attractive positions accessible to the lower middle-class. However, Theology was not offered at the Hohe Karlsschule, and Duke Carl Eugen of Württemberg decided that Schiller should study Law, after failing in which he was allowed to study Medicine. Ergo, although Schiller defiantly pursued a career as a dramatist and outspoken opponent of personal, organized, and state religion as an adult, and although he only once ironically wrote of his childhood ambition to be a clergyman (NA 23:121), he can still be broadly considered a religious person until his death.* This anecdote from Schiller's childhood has a bookend in the highly questionable testimony of Schiller's servant Rudolph and his sister-in-law Caroline von Wolzogen that Schiller had a religious experience on his deathbed (High 2012, 154-155). This evidence (and the invalid syllogism that it almost invariably supports) comprises the shaky *sine qua non* of the case for Schiller's religion; it nonetheless has a firm place in canonical Schiller reception, as documented below.

With few exceptions — notably in works by Joseph Gostwick (1882), Peter André Alt (2004), Norbert Oellers (2006), and Manfred Misch (1998, 2011)⁸ — the history of attempts to articulate Schiller's attitudes toward religion is one marked by pseudo-scholarly sectarianism, cooptive stretches of evidence, and inflations of the significance of plausible religious influences that do not enlighten and should not persuade.⁹ Foremost, these constitute Christian usurpations and post-deathbed conversion attempts contingent on the willful misunderstanding and Christianization of Schiller's many uses of almost exclusively pagan metaphysical metaphor and the refusal or inability to read allegorically.¹⁰ Indeed, Schiller's gods, as Henry Hatfield put it in 1964, are "romantic gods [...] less real, less actual; we are in the world of mythology, of aesthetic semblance [...] the Greek divinities were fictions."¹¹ In spite of such sensible insights into the metaphorical nature of Schiller's gods (and heavens), in spite

of Schiller's recasting of Moses from a prophet on a literally divine mission to a brilliant politician and law-giver on an earthly mission,¹² and in spite of Schiller's easily documented hostility toward organized religions, prophets, and their gods, the case for Schiller the secularist remains a struggle some two hundred years after the period Schiller described as "Zeiten des Unglaubens" (NA 32:154).

As a result, long held and widespread beliefs (as opposed to proofs) regard Schiller as "homo religiosus,"¹³ and there is abundant secondary literature on his ostensible "religion" (Sell 1904),¹⁴ "essentially religious" mind (Bulwer-Lytton 1844),¹⁵ "religiosity" (von Wiese 1959),¹⁶ or "spirituality";¹⁷ his "undogmatic Protestantism" (Fricke 1927),¹⁸ "closet Catholicism" (Rehm 1951),¹⁹ or "Swabian Pietism" (as a religion with a god, not as an environment or dialect; McCradle 1986).²⁰ On a more theoretical level, the, in the context of Schillerian thought, oxymoronic concepts of "Religionsphilosophie,"²¹ "das religiös-Sittliche,"²² "das religiös Erhabene,"²³ "Liebesreligion,"²⁴ "Vernunftreligion" (as opposed to secular moral-aesthetic philosophy),²⁵ and the popular-anecdotal concept of Schiller's moral-aesthetics as "Ersatzreligion" (philosophy as a substitute religion) are self-evidently confused directions that necessarily falsely equate religion (unsubstantiated belief) and obedience with reason and moral philosophy (the study of knowledge and experience). Logically speaking, reason is not a substitute for religion, religion is a substitute for reason, and Schiller himself argued early, often, and clearly enough that religion is merely a "Surrogat der wahren Tugend" (1793; NA 26:330-331), and that true virtue can only be achieved through the cultivation of ennobled reason or "Veredlung des Charakters" (1795; NA 20:332).

Religious conflict between states, sects, and individuals explicitly inform a majority of Schiller's dramas and a number of his poems and essays. Schiller's engagement with religious problems ranges from brief references — e.g., the murder of Huguenots by Catholics in Paris in *Die Schaubühne als moralische Anstalt* (1784) — to key plot elements — religious entrapment and conversion of a prince in *Der Geisterseher* (1789) — to a central source of political conflict in *Don Karlos* (1787), *Die Geschichte des Abfalls der vereinigten Niederlande von der Spanischen Regierung* (1788), *Die Geschichte des Dreyßigjährigen Kriegs* (1791-92), *Wallenstein* (1799), and *Maria Stuart* (1800), to name only a few examples. Common to these historical settings is the limited and limiting primary concern of the religious freedom movements they engage — the relative freedom of one oppressed group (e.g., Dutch Protestants) to pursue a religion other than that imposed on them by another group (e.g., Spanish Catholics). However, the freedom of a prince to choose which beliefs will be imposed on his subjects (state religion), like the freedom of a populace to choose native over foreign tyranny, constitutes freedom in only the weakest sense, one that implicitly precludes the rational, common constitutional goal of all who suffer religious intolerance — individual freedom *from* (not *of*) all forms of ideological coercion.²⁶

The present study's titular distinction between freedom *of* religion and freedom *from* religion is intended to

emphasize the prerequisites for unfettered exercise of freedom of thought (*Gedankenfreiheit*) and freedom of conscience (*Gewissensfreiheit*); namely, not only the guaranty of freedom to associate with one of the state-approved religions, but the freedom to choose none of them and the guarantee of freedom from any state, church, majority, or minority coercion through religion. Schiller's *Wallenstein* trilogy (1798-1800) portrays a remarkable exception to the princely prerogative to choose one religion for his subjects over another. Although there is nothing particularly moving about the off-stage death of Wallenstein in *Wallensteins Tod*, his demise brings about two directly related tragedies, 1) the lost opportunity to avoid another decade and a half of religious war (1634-1648), and 2) the lost potential of a large central-European state, Bohemia, that has no state religion. Regardless of the Capuchin Friar's accusations that Wallenstein is "[...] ein Sündenvater und muffiger Ketzler," who "[r]uhmte sich mit seinem gottlosen Mund" (NA 8:33), Wallenstein has become a threat to the Catholic and Protestant empires precisely because he is a magnet for soldiers who have abandoned either the Protestant King of Sweden or the Catholic Austrian Emperor. Arguably his most quotable soldier, the First Jäger, initially abandoned the Protestant army due to coerced piety — "Bei Gustav dem Schweden, dem Leuteplager! / Der machte eine Kirch aus seinem Lager, / Ließ Betstunde halten, des Morgens gleich / Bei der Reveille, und beim Zapfenstreich" (NA 8:20) — then left the Emperor's service due to a lack of personal freedom (NA 8:22). After explaining all of this, he threatens to murder the Capuchin Friar, an unwelcome representative of Catholicism at the camp, who criticizes Wallenstein's lack of religion: "[v]erläugnet wie Petrus seinen Meister und Herrn [...]" (NA 8:33). According to the First Jäger, for all of the obvious problems caused by the unfettered freedom of the soldiers, Wallenstein's camp exhibits three untimely constitutional premises for the seventeenth century: freedom of thought and speech — "Was ich denke, das darf ich sagen. / Das Wort ist frei, sagt der General" (NA 8:23) — and freedom from religion — "Was nicht verboten ist, ist erlaubt; / Da fragt niemand, was einer glaubt" (NA 8:22). Some 150 years after the death of Wallenstein, *Gedankenfreiheit* and *Gewissensfreiheit* are the parallel considerations that bind Schiller's *Don Karlos* and the constitutional separation of church and state that informs the U.S. "Bill of Rights" and the French "Declaration of the Rights of Man and the Citizen" (introduced nearly simultaneously in 1789). Both declare the explicit guarantees of the individual right to express opinions on religion, and the freedom not to believe in, nor need feign, the observation of any and all conventions of faith, without consequence.

II.

The concepts of the separation of church and state, legal protections of freedom of religion, and freedom of thought and speech have a complicated history of advocates and opponents, from Moses to Socrates to today.²⁷ In the late eighteenth century, a new demand appears in works that focus on the constitutional guaranty of universal freedom *from* religion — the advocacy of a state in which no individual can legally be subjected to religious coercion. While Schiller was a college student at the

Hohe Karlsschule in the late 1770s, developments toward the legal codification of religious freedom were swift. Inherent to the Scottish eudemonism central to Thomas Jefferson's education at the College of William and Mary and to Schiller's education at the Hohe Karlsschule is a constitutional concern for the rights of the most vulnerable individual and a focus on freedom and disinterested virtue that makes earthly happiness and the republic itself essentially incompatible with the coercive political, social, and private functions of organized religion.²⁸ The focus on the quality of life — without any serious consideration of an afterlife — and the accompanying concern for religious freedom and earthly justice strongly inform the documents of the American War of Independence, a rebellion which had in large part legitimized the pursuit of happiness as an actual goal of politics. The "Virginia Declaration of Rights," written by George Mason (assisted by James Madison) of 12 June 1776 declares that "all men are equally entitled to the free exercise of religion, according to the dictates of conscience."²⁹ Thomas Jefferson's "Declaration of Independence," ratified on 4 July 1776, proclaimed that the guiding principle of all human activity is "the pursuit of Happiness" and conspicuously replaces traditional church-state rhetoric with deist moral philosophy.³⁰ Looking back fifty years later, Jefferson emphasized the link between individual autonomy and freedom from religion, calling the "Declaration of Independence," "the signal of arousing men to burst the chains under which monkish ignorance and superstition had persuaded them to bind themselves, and to assume the blessings and security of self government."³¹

Less than a year later, in 1777, Jefferson drafted the "Virginia Statute on Religious Freedom" (ratified in 1779), which demonstrates a rapid paradigm shift in liberal views on the difference between freedom *of* religion — the goal of which is tolerance of different beliefs — and freedom *from* religion, which encompasses freedom of thought or opinion, including the protection of individuals who choose to criticize or wholly ignore religion:

[...] no man shall be compelled to frequent or support any religious worship, place, or ministry whatsoever, nor shall be enforced, restrained, molested, or burthened in his body or goods, nor shall otherwise suffer on account of his religious opinions or belief, but that all men shall be free to profess, and by argument to maintain, their opinions in matters of Religion, and that the same shall in no wise diminish, enlarge or affect their civil capacities.³²

The "Virginia Statute on Religious Freedom" provided the language for the first article of the United States "Bill of Rights" adopted by the House of Representatives on 21 August 1789, which became the First Amendment to the US Constitution (ratified 15 December 1791), in which the "separation of Church and State" is implied and de facto codified: "Congress shall make no law respecting an establishment of religion, or prohibiting the free exercise thereof; or abridging the freedom of speech, or of the press [...]."³³ In a letter to representatives of the Danbury Baptist Church in 1802, Jefferson explains that the goal of the "Establishment Clause" is "building a wall of separation between Church & State."³⁴

These same three concerns, human happiness, religious freedom, and earthly justice (among others), inform the documents of the French Revolution of 1789. The same week that the US “Bill of Rights” was adopted, indeed only five days later, the French “Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen” was adopted by the National Assembly in Paris on 26 August 1789, including Article 10: “No one shall be disquieted on account of his opinions, including his religious views, provided their manifestation does not disturb the public order established by law.”³⁵ In Maximilian de Robespierre’s “Festival of the Supreme Being” speech, delivered on 8 June 1794, Robespierre articulates a political philosophy of happiness that was to be observed as if it were a religion handed down and enforced by a deistic creator: “He [the Supreme Being] created men to help each other, to love each other mutually, and to attain to happiness by the way of virtue.”³⁶ Note that the date of “Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen” is three years to the day prior to the vote to honor seventeen international revolutionary heroes on 26 August 1792, including Schiller. As will be documented below, Schiller was an excellent choice for this distinction due both to his belief in a teleology of happiness and his popular writings portraying religion and the church state as primary barriers to a republic based on disinterested virtue and the freedom and happiness of the individual.

III.

Schiller’s first theoretical work on freedom is the speech, “Gehört allzuviel Güte, Leutseeligkeit und große Freygebigkeit im engsten Verstande zur Tugend?,” which Schiller wrote at the age of nineteen in 1779. In keeping with the practice established in his earliest poems, in the First Virtue Speech, Schiller works on a number of metaphorical registers, including pagan imagery and biblical imagery from both the Old and New Testaments.³⁷ In the fifth of twenty-three paragraphs, an unrecognizable version of a metaphorical creator-philosopher-scientist who loves humankind opens a series of questions that explain the role of virtue in the universe: “Was wars, das den Weisesten leitete, eine Welt aus dem Chaos zu erheben? [...] Was wars das den Liebenden leitete, der neu gebohrnen Welt Ordnung und Wohlklang zu geben durch ewige unwandelbare Gesetze?” (NA 20:4). The answer, the fusion of endless love and endless wisdom, appears less relevant to religion and physics than to politics and the ultimate harmony of civilization. In the seventh paragraph, the highest “Gotheit” (deity; NA 20:5) is Jupiter. In the fifteenth paragraph, Schiller addresses an entirely nondescript nature deity in invoking Klopstock’s ode, “Für den König” (NA 20:7, NA21:113). The eighteenth paragraph is dedicated to love (NA 20:7), which is first “die Krone der Tugend” (NA 20:7) and then the “Erstgebohrne des Himmels” (NA 20:7), and features four exhortations to bow before this concept of love, including one directed to nature, one to the human, one to an angel, and one to all (NA 20:7-8). In the nineteenth paragraph, “Weißheit! Schönste Gespielin der Liebe” appears as “das Meisterwerk Gottes” and “des Schöpfers großherrlicher Plan” (NA 20:8). These references are anchored in seven exhortations to worship “Weißheit,” which appears as a

synonym for the deist concepts of “große Unendliche Natur” and “ewiges Uhrwerk” (NA 20:8). The paragraph ends with a final command to worship love, wisdom, and “Tugend” (NA 20:8). In the twentieth paragraph, Schiller appeals to the “Göttin der Wohlthätigkeit” (NA 20:8).³⁸ There is no way to conclude that this kaleidoscope of metaphors contains anything more than an allegorical reference to any orthodox form of Christianity. On the contrary, the elevation of wisdom to a metaphorical deity necessarily serves to reject and displace most of what religion has to offer. The thesis not only rejects the supernatural-irrational aspects of religion, but also the moral philosophy, since Schiller — at age nineteen and at the very beginning of his career — has just established that virtue is impossible without freedom from external and internal coercion, and thus impossible within the confines of religion.

Significantly, the speech revolves around church-state a miscarriage of justice and Schiller’s long-time hero, Socrates,³⁹ who was tried and executed for his disrespect for the gods by a jury pretending to be upholding a divine will, culminating in Socrates’ choice of death and freedom over life and coercion. The most remarkable comment on virtue and religion comes in the final two paragraphs (15-16) of the third segment (on moral resistance, paragraphs 12-16). Again returning to “die ächte Tugend des Weisen” (NA 20:7) as a role model, Schiller switches metaphorical registers from the judgment of a powerful Old Testament God — who knows the source of all superficially good deeds at their conception and rewards or punishes them before they reach fruition (an allusion to Socrates’ concept of retribution in the here and now) — to the power of virtue over the ever-changing demands of gods throughout history and thus the ever-changing pseudo-virtue of religion: “Ihm [dem Weisen] ist sie [die Tugend] ein mächtiger Harnisch gegentzönd den Donnern des Himmels ein gewaltiger Schirm wenn zu Trümmern gehen die Himmel, wenn die Scheintugend, wie vor dem Winde Spreu hinwegflattert” (NA 20:7). The only logical conclusion to be achieved here is that while the virtue and wisdom of a Socrates endure, both the appearance of virtue and popular evolving religious visions of heaven do not. Note Schiller’s uses of “Himmel” (heaven) as both a singular and a plural noun. “Himmel” is a collective noun that already can mean “the heavens,” thus Schiller’s unusual use of the plural form “die Himmel” would appear to indicate a coming age when all non-metaphorical concepts of the realm of gods will collapse and blow away like chaff.⁴⁰ Left standing will be the sage, Socrates, in his impenetrable virtue. Despite the practical limits of freedom of speech at the Hohe Karlschule, where daily prayer and an intensive curriculum in religion were mandatory, Christ warrants little more than a few veiled mentions in Schiller’s oeuvre, whereas Socrates continues to be an important figure, and Schiller’s introduction to the First Virtue Speech implies that Socrates is most sublime because of — not in spite of — his ignorance of Judeo-Christian revelation: “Ich sehe den erhabensten Geist, den je das Altertum gebahr, dem nie dämmerte der Offenbarung Gottes ein blasser Wiederstrahl” (NA 20:3). Of the three positive role models for virtue mentioned by name, Socrates; Roman Emperor and

stoic philosopher Marcus Aurelius (121-180 CE; NA 20:8), who promoted stoicism over Christianity; and Cathmor, the paragon of virtue in James Macpherson's *Ossian* (1760; NA 20:8); all three are pagans (at best).

In his second dissertation of 1780, *Ueber den Zusammenhang der thierischen Natur des Menschen mit seiner geistigen*, Schiller returns to the development of civilizations, drawing attention to the very earthly and human origins of the religious tribe or church state, which results from a conscious manipulation of the masses by those who know best that religions represent historical-political stages in the evolution of communities: "Städte werden bevestiget, Staaten errichtet, mit den Staaten entstehen bürgerliche Pflichten und Rechte, Künste, Ziffern, Gesezbücher, schlaue Priester — und Götter" (NA 20:54). Note that in Schiller's universal historical view, after law books, as a rule, clever priests precede god(s), which is only logical, because, as Schiller's "An die Freude" implies, gods are projections that judge whatever the priests and adherents say they do.

Approximately one year later, in act II of *Die Räuber* (1781), Schiller's Karl Moor delivers a scathing criticism of priestcraft at work, directly to a priest, in his portrayal of the hypocritical enforcement of tribal state values: "Da donnern sie Sanftmuth und Duldung aus ihren Wolken, und bringen dem Gott der Liebe Menschenopfer wie einem feuerarmigen Moloch—predigen Liebe des Nächsten, und fluchen den achzigjährigen Blinden von ihren Thüren hinweg: stürmen wider den Geiz und haben Peru um goldner Spangen willen entvölkert und die Heyden wie Zugvieh vor ihre Wagen gespannt" (NA 3:70). To summarize, there is more than enough in Schiller's earliest works at the Karlsschule to undo the notion that his early desire to become a minister might translate into a positive view of the role of religion in contemporary society in his adulthood. On the contrary, Schiller's analysis of Socrates as the the wisest and most sublime thinker of antiquity outlines the freedom-from-religion discourse that would inform his later works.

IV.

If the few references in Schiller's Karlsschule works paint religion as a roadblock to true virtue at best and as a tool of enslavement and murder at worst, Schiller's post-doctoral works are more direct in regard to the role of aesthetics and morality in the ultimate evolution from the church state to the ideal of a secular republic. In 1784, in "Die Schaubühne als Moralische Anstalt," Schiller demonstrates the inhumane consequences of the religious state in action: "Christus Religion war das Feldgeschrei, als man Amerika entvölkerte — Christus Religion zu verherrlichen [...] schoss Karl der Neunte auf die fliehenden Hugenotten zu Paris" (NA 20:89-90). Less direct, yet more insidiously subversive, is the poem that would go on to become an almost instant folk song long before the appearance of Beethoven's melody in 1824. Schiller's ode "An die Freude" is often falsely invoked as a text that exemplifies his own personal dualistic hovering between the secular and the religious, a misreading on a basic level that results in further canonical misinterpretations. Schiller's admittedly confusing references to heaven, God, and religion somehow become foremost Christian concepts in the eyes of readers,⁴¹ although the poem itself

begins with the idea that "joy" is a metaphorical daughter who descends specifically from "Elysium" ("in the world of mythology, of aesthetic semblance"; Hatfield, 120). The poem is a good example of Schiller mixing metaphors in an attempt to invite the largest and most diverse possible audience to entertain the idea of the most daring ideal of a human republic (without giving censors much solid ground on which to stand). Here, Schiller employs a blur of (mostly ancient Greek and deist) metaphors for joy with a disorienting variety of personal pronouns (er, sie, es, ihn) and possessive pronouns (dein, ihr) to create a syllogism, concluding that the pursuit of happiness is nature's prime drive — and that any word for "gods" is a multidimensional metaphor for the organizing principle of the cosmos, which is individual joy and one of its many contributing conditions, political happiness.⁴² It follows that "Gott" (who is Zeus/Jupiter, a deity nobody believes in), "ein lieber Vater," "der Unbekannte," "de[r] Schöpfer," "Göttern," "de[r] gute[] Geist," and "der Sternenrichter" are all metaphorical projections for the ultimate earthly end that humans (like worms and cherubs) desire. "An die Freude" is thus first a matter of church and state because it is a public portrayal of pagan and other religious concepts as expressions of strictly human desires. Second, it is a matter of church and state because its cosmopolitan concept of brotherhood implies the disestablishment of cultural orthodoxies that persecute difference, be it the differences between beggars and princes or those that distinguish worms, cherubs, and Zeus/Jupiter. Third, it is a document of the age of secular revolution in that its concept of universal freedom and happiness displaces the coerced uniformity of the church state and specifically exiles those who cannot be human (princes and, by implication, the sexless, joyless Trinitarian blur of "Die Götter Griechenlandes"): "Und wer's nie gekonnt, der stehle / weinend sich aus diesem Bund!" (NA 1: 169). Fourth, the final instance of coerced uniformity of opinion and behavior — divine judgment — is erased in the line "richtet Gott wie wir gerichtet" (NA 1:171), which states that humans judge first (present perfect) and God agrees (present tense), evidently because God is a projection of human beliefs. Thus, here, too, earthly judgment is the only judgment that matters. Finally, as Dieter Hildebrandt has documented, it is a matter of church and state because representatives of the most repressed forms of religious fundamentalist thought immediately, predictably, and accurately attacked the poem and the poet for blasphemy.⁴³

V.

Schiller's subsequent early works portray a dim view of the fear of divine judgement and of heaven as the reward for a life of self-denial.⁴⁴ In the poem "Resignation," Schiller describes the promise of the afterlife as "Ein Lügenbild lebendiger Gestalten" and paints a picture of the afterlife as "decay" (Verwesung) "in the cold shelter of the grave" (in den kalten Behausungen des Grabes). Schiller's poem recasts the choice between enjoying life on Earth, "Freude," or waiting for happiness in eternity as that between self-deception, "Hoffnung," and plausible, present, enjoyable reality, "Genuß" (NA 1:168). Thus, those who can believe are rewarded with a facile answer to life's unanswerable questions; those who do not be-

lieve are rewarded with earthly happiness: “Genieße, wer nicht glauben kann [...] Wer glauben kann, entbehre” (NA 1:168). The final strophe of “Resignation” restates the same with even more clarity: the reward for faith is the absence of uncertainty; but it is a mistake to trade a minute of earthly happiness for the empty “shadow” promise of compensation from a “liar” (religion) in the service of “despots,”⁴⁵ and whatever earthly happiness one denies at the moment, no eternity will give back.⁴⁶ Ergo, according to the poem, in the great decision between here and now or then and there, there is no “there.” This view is supported by the very clearly stated secular position on divine judgment: “Die Weltgeschichte ist das Weltgericht” (NA 1:168).⁴⁷ Thus, in “Resignation,” the value of life, love, and morality is an earthly affair; Judgment Day is nothing less than a metaphor for the reception of life on Earth, while divine judgment, taken literally, is nothing more than an empty threat.⁴⁸

In 1788, the once somewhat speculative evidence of Schiller’s hostility toward organized religion was confirmed to alert members of the reading public with the publication of “Die Götter Griechenlandes.” Again, one of the main topics is earthly justice and the negative function of religion. Here, the father/son/holy ghost as judge appears as an emotionless instance of negative duties, a distant and immortal (and thus alien) usurper who displaces the mild Greek judge, who was a mortal’s offspring: “Nach der Geister schrecklichen Gesetzen / richtete kein Heiliger Barbar” (NA 1:193). Schiller contrasts Christianity’s prophet-god of implausible virgin birth and indisputable revelation with typological, metaphorical, mythological, and fictional Greek heroes with mothers who have a healthy enough relationship to the sinful facts of human life to get pregnant through the traditional method. The Greek gods’ proximity to human life and love — “Zwischen Menschen, Göttern und Heroen / knüpfte Amor einen schönen Bund” (NA 1:191) — and to the realization of a happier human era stands in stark contrast to the grim, punitive, lifeless, joyless, sexless “Entsagen” (NA 1:193) of Christianity. On the political freedom and tolerance front, embarking from the Greek model, Schiller establishes that tribal mythologies once embraced a broad spectrum of aesthetic-moral projections of freedom (“Vorstellungsart”; NA 25:167), and only later became aesthetic-moral tools of coercion in the hands of the church state. On a moral and legal front, Schiller demonstrates the inappropriateness of a divine judge, who could not possibly commiserate with mortal inhabitants of the earth, those “zarte Wesen, die ein Weib gebar” (NA 1:193), implying that, aside from the inevitable laws of nature, only humans can (and do) give laws to humans. A common thread in Schiller’s criticisms is the belief that, by the late eighteenth century, religion had become a formidable road block to both truth and true morality, which are only possible without external control of any kind, and specifically without church, state, and mob coercion.⁴⁹ Again, as if to comically demonstrate the truth of the threat of coerced uniformity, Schiller was immediately publicly accused of blasphemy.⁵⁰ According to Novalis, as a result of the poem, Schiller was being publicly denounced as an atheist.⁵¹

Reception of “Die Götter Griechenlandes” is divided into clear religious and secularist camps.⁵² In the August 1788 edition of *Deutsches Museum*, poet Friedrich Leopold Graf zu Stolberg (1750-1819) published the most prominent attack on Schiller and his “gods,” “Gedanken ueber Herrn Schillers Gedicht: ‘Die Götter Griechenlandes.’” Stolberg specifically cites the eleventh strophe as blasphemy, and as the demonstration of “das traurige Verhältnis, in welchem der Naturalist mit der Gottheit steht.”⁵³ Significantly, Stolberg is offended by the philosophy of the empiricist “naturalist,” who not only requires no deity, since the laws of nature suffice, but who also believes that modern Christianity is a roadblock to freedom, while insisting on freedom of speech in the matter. Two contemporary defenses of freedom of speech — one secularist, one Christian — written by Georg Forster (1754-1794) and Novalis (1772-1801) come to similar conclusions regarding freedom of speech, despite Schiller’s blasphemy, anti-Christian rhetoric, and ostensible atheism. The most prominent defense of Schiller’s poem is Forster’s “Fragment eines Briefes an einen deutschen Schriftsteller über Schillers ‘Götter Griechenlandes’” in the May 1789 edition of *Neue Litteratur und Voelkerkunde*. Whereas Schiller and Körner address only the freedom of speech issue, Forster directly addresses Stolberg’s charge of blasphemy (“Gotteslästerung”) and the possibility of actual charges of blasphemy (“Religionsvergehen”). Significantly, Forster concedes that Schiller may be “ein Lästere” (Forster 63) and “im Herzen ein Heide” (Forster 58), but argues that Schiller nonetheless has a right to his opinion and freedom of speech.⁵⁴

During the same period, Novalis composes both a defense of Schiller’s poem — “Apologie von Friedrich Schiller” (Novalis 2:24-25) — and a fragmentary discussion of atheism that appears to be a complementary piece on Schiller: “Kann ein Atheist auch moralisch tugendhaft aus Grundsätzen seyn?,” both undated. Novalis’ defense of freedom of speech indicates that contemporary criticism of the poem indeed included charges of atheism. In his fragment on morality and atheism, Novalis recognizes at least two sub-categories of atheists, evidently common enough to distinguish — “Ich spreche nicht von Atheisten aus Mode sondern [von] wirklich überzeugten” — and proceeds to reduce atheism to two Schillerian concepts, the means, “virtue” — “Er fühlt die Wonne der seligen geräuschlosen Tugend” — and the end, “joy” — “Ein Atheist braucht nicht trübe zu seyn, sondern freudig, weil Freude ihn Gottheit ist und sie alles auf den gegenwärtigen Augenblick einschränken.”⁵⁵ With that, Novalis delivers a precise and concise explanation of Schiller’s division between the benefits of religious belief (peace of mind in the belief in the afterlife as sole compensation for joyless obedience and self-denial) and non-belief (the freedom to enjoy life here and now) in the poem “Resignation”; and of the logic of metaphor in Schiller’s secularist ode, “An die Freude,” in which all metaphysical references are metaphors for the common goal of all existence — earthly happiness, that is, freedom from coercion, both external and internal.

VI.

In the same year, in *Die Geschichte des Abfalls der vereinigten Niederlande von der Spanischen Regierung* (1788), Schiller elaborates on how the church state (here Philipp II and the Inquisition) creates the illusion of civilization through enforced uniformity, and how religion enslaves and impoverishes humanity by harnessing common human hopes and fears to terrorize and reduce populations to enduring ignorance and crude tribalism:

Sie [die Religion] findet Hoffnung und Furcht in jede Menschenbrust gesäet; indem sie sich dieser Triebe bemächtigt, diese Triebe *Einem* Gegenstand unterjocht, hat sie Millionen selbständiger Wesen in ein einförmiges Abstrakt verwandelt. Die unendliche Mannichfaltigkeit der menschlichen Willkür verwirrt ihren Beherrscher jezt nicht mehr—jezt giebt es ein allgemeines Uebel und ein allgemeines Gut, das er zeigen und entziehen kann, das auch da, wo er *nicht* ist, mit ihm einverstanden wirkt. Jezt giebt es eine Gränze, an welcher die Freiheit still steht, eine ehrwürdige heilige Linie, nach welcher alle streitende Bewegungen des Willens zuletzt einlenken müssen. Das gemeinschaftliche Ziel des Despotismus und des Priestertums ist *Einförmigkeit*, und Einförmigkeit ist ein nothwendiges Hilfsmittel der menschlichen Armuth und Beschränkung. (NA 17:55)

Thus, religion here results in a pseudo-civilization that features a philosophy based on falsehoods and the appearance of peace based on coercion. After the government, the primary beneficiaries of this enslavement are the priests and, to a lesser extent, the followers of the majority sect. Schiller concludes: “Die goldene Zeit der Geistlichkeit fiel immer in die Gefangenschaft des menschlichen Geistes” (NA 17:55).

When Heinrich Heine wrote: “Schiller schrieb für die großen Ideen der Revolution, er zerstörte die geistigen Bastillen, er baute an dem Tempel der Freiheit, und zwar an jenem ganz großen Tempel, der alle Nationen, gleich einer einzigen Brüdergemeinde, umschließen soll; er war Kosmopolit,”⁵⁶ he was talking about the author of *Don Karlos*. It is difficult to imagine a more cosmopolitan drama: the story of a Spanish king, the Dutch liberation movement, and the universal historical causes of liberation, self-determination, and the separation of church and state. Indeed, though the constitutional concept of the separation of church and state appears in a large number of Schiller’s literary, historical, and theatrical works, nowhere does it appear more prominently than in *Don Karlos* and in his *Briefe über Don Karlos* (1787), a series of published letters defending the unity of the drama. In the eighth of the *Briefe über Don Karlos*, Schiller moves quickly from the “Lieblingsgegenstand unseres Jahrhunderts” (NA 22:162), “die Verbreitung reinerer sanfterer Humanität” to “die höchstmögliche Freiheit der Individuen bei des Staats höchster Blüte” (NA 26:162). *Don Karlos* offers all the ingredients of the anti-church-state revolution: “Freiheitssinn mit Despotismus im Kampfe, die Fesseln der Dummheit zerbrochen, tausendjährige Vorurteile erschüttert, eine Nation, die ihre Menschenrechte wieder fodert, republikanische Tugenden in Ausübung gebracht, hellere Begriffe im Umlauf, die Köpfe in Gärung, die Gemüther von einem begeisterten Interesse gehoben” (NA 22:162). This all sounds very eighteenth-century, and not very sixteenth-century. In de-

fense of the untimely nature of Posa’s republicanism, Schiller argues that it is precisely the repressive environment of the Inquisition that inspires it, one informed by servitude and religion: “Das entgegengesetzte Elend der Sklaverei und des Aberglaubens zieht sie [seine Seele] immer fester und fester an diese Lieblingswelt; die schönsten Träume der Freiheit werden ja im Kerker geträumt. [...] das kühnste Ideal einer Menschenrepublik, allgemeiner Duldung und Gewissensfreiheit, wo konnte es besser und wo natürlicher zur Welt geboren werden als in der Nähe Philipps und seiner Inquisition?” (NA 22:141). The hallmark of this particular form of church-state pseudo-civilization, as Schiller’s Marquis Posa describes it sarcastically, is “die Ruhe eines Kirchhofs” (NA 6:190), not the isolation of the mere “Kerker” mentioned above, nor even the less specific term “Friedhof,” but the deathly silence of a cemetery run by a church.

The historical situation stands in the most grave contrast to Posa’s “heitre menschliche Philosophie,” a philosophy of reason both humane and of human — not divine — origin. The goal of this philosophy “[w]ird [...] über den Prinzen hinaus gerückt” (NA 22:161), indeed, it regards “[d]as große Schicksal eines ganzen Staats, das Glück des menschlichen Geschlechts auf viele Generationen” (NA 22:161). The ultimate consideration is, as Schiller summarizes, neither friendship nor love between the main characters, but “ein Enthusiastischer Entwurf” (NA 22:164), and, according to Schiller, Posa’s path is not mere “Reformantenbahn” (NA 22:164), but revolution and constitution. The tenth letter ends with the statement that the close reader will recognize the principles of Montesquieu in *Don Karlos*, and with this Schiller can only mean the separation of powers and the case for constitution. The twelfth letter includes a lengthy discussion of the parallel significances of the deaths of Posa and Lykurgus as the demonstrative sacrificial means to make the constitution last (NA 22:174). Significantly, Schiller elaborates the concept of tolerance with that of freedom of conscience. The first instance of tolerance addressed, “Duldung,” is at best a practical guideline; the second, “Gewissensfreiheit” is a positive legal concept that is practically enforceable. Having established with great conviction in the central audience scene of *Don Karlos* that “Glückseligkeit” is the ultimate goal of Posa’s pursuits, here in the subsequent paragraph of the second letter on *Don Karlos*, Schiller categorizes “Gewissensfreiheit” as one of the republican virtues that foremost informs Posa’s thought and as the most sublime of all ideas (NA 22:141). In the penultimate paragraph of the second letter, Schiller uses the term “Wahrheit” three times to describe “Gewissensfreiheit,” which he concludes is the single republican virtue most worth dying for. This being the case, and since Posa’s death is the central mechanism of the drama, freedom of conscience is therefore arguably its central theme according to Schiller’s logic.

Marquis Posa is both fictionalized and dead, but is as allegorically immortal as Socrates in his impenetrable virtue; it is important to be clear what he died for. First, tolerance alone was never his ultimate goal, nor was any other moderate reform, nor did he die to save his friend Karlos, as even Philipp II recognizes in the play: “Für einen Knaben stirbt / ein Posa nicht” (NA 6:320). Speculation in the play posits that Posa is a Protestant convert, a

theory Posa himself disputes in his dialogue with Philipp: “Ihr Glaube, Sire, ist auch / der meinige” (NA 6:184). Thus Posa considers himself to be a Catholic, but a very different Catholic from those at Philipp’s court; his empathy for others leads him to seek the ideal starting point for a republican revolution against the King of Christianity that will result in constitutional guarantees, as Schiller writes in the third letter:

Der Geist der Völker wird von ihm studiert, ihre Kräfte, ihre Hilfsmittel abgewogen, ihre Verfassungen geprüft [...] feuriger für dieses grosse Ganze entzündet, das ihm in so vielen Individuen vergegenwärtigt war, so kommt er jetzt von der grossen Ernte zurück, brennend von Sehnsucht, einen Schauplatz zu finden, auf welchem er diese Ideale realisieren, diese gesammelten Schätze in Anwendung bringen könnte. Flanderns Zustand bietet sich ihm dar. Alles findet sich zu einer Revolution zubereitet. [...] Sein Ideal republikanischer Freiheit kann kein günstigeres Moment und keinen empfänglicheren Boden finden. (NA 22: 146-147)

In the ninth letter on *Don Karlos*, Schiller addresses the formula for Spanish despotism itself. If, as Schiller wrote in the poem “Resignation,” “religion is a liar in the service of despots,” and if the “common aim of despotism and of priestcraft is uniformity, and uniformity is a necessary expedient of human poverty and imperfection” (NA 17:55), then among the worst imaginable of all possible governments would be the worldly, supra-national despot in the service of the religious liar. This is how Schiller describes the relationship between Philipp and the Grand Inquisitor both in the drama (act V, scene 10; NA 6:326-334) and in the ninth of the *Briefe über Don Karlos*: “den Despoten [...], vor welchem man in fernen Weltteilen zittert, sehen wir von einem herrischen Priester eine erniedrigende Rechenschaft ablegen und eine leichte Übertretung mit einer schimpflichen Züchtigung büßen” (NA 22:166). Indeed, the final scene reinforces the fact that even the King of Spain himself would be better served by the separation of church and state.

Since Schiller has already confirmed that (his) Posa’s goal (and not the goal of the Netherlands in the sixteenth century) is a revolution led by Karlos to realize eighteenth-century constitutional ideals, including freedom of religion, Schiller’s ostensible portrayal of sixteenth-century Spain would appear to be just one short step from the separation of church and state and freedom from religion. In act II, scene 10, Schiller introduces the secular state. Here, the ultimate threat to the disingenuous Christians at Philipp’s court, according to the King’s Confessor Domingo in his report to Duke Alba, is not the liberation of the Netherlands, and neither their Protestantism, nor even a merely political rebellion against Philipp by Prince Karlos and Marquis Posa, but the threat to the Inquisition’s church state posed by Karlos’ secular philosophy and Posa’s vision of a republic. Domingo’s testimony features the now familiar Schillerian division between the replacement virtue of faith (pseudo-civilization) and the new, according to Schiller in 1779, *true*, virtue of reason:

Der Infant / (Ich kenn’ ihn – ich durchdringe seine Seele) / Hegt einen schrecklichen Entwurf — Toledo — / Den rasenden Entwurf, Regent zu sein / Und unsern heil’gen Glauben zu entbeh-

ren. — / Sein Herz entglüht für eine neue Tugend, / Die, stolz und sicher und sich selbst genug, / Von keinem Glauben betteln will. — Er denkt! / Sein Kopf entbrennt von einer seltsamen / Chimäre — Er verehrt den Menschen — Herzog, / Ob er zu unserm König taugt? (NA 6:123-124).

A “self-sufficient” virtue — “sich selbst genug” — is precisely the concept of virtue discussed in Schiller’s First Virtue Essay of 1779. Virtuous acts are, by Schiller’s definition, disinterested and thus free from both external (i.e., state or church) and internal (the imbalance of either reason or feeling) coercion. Indeed, the overarching goal of Schiller’s moral-aesthetic writings, the happiness of the individual through the cultivation of ennobled reason, is in fact diametrically opposed to the political, social, and private functions of organized religion. Each of these functions is coercive, thus each hinders progress toward true civic virtue, the former two through state and tribal enforcement, the latter one through postponing the development of ennobled reason. Like Socrates before them, both Posa, and, after him, Karlos have achieved this freedom from external and internal forms of coercion and are prepared to die for the freedom of others before Posa is shot dead and Karlos arrested for offenses punishable by death.

The untimely demand for the separation of church and state in sixteenth-century Spain would seem alienating if not for the fact that Schiller had already long established a consistent program of (and an uncanny ability for) weaving a number of historical and metaphorical models together to create a singular transcendent impression. As ever, Schiller is much less interested in historical truth within historical context than he is in the contemporary and future value of poetic and philosophical truth, which is the point of his practiced form of universal history.⁵⁷ Throughout the play, Schiller combines the problems of the Dutch provinces with the Scottish Enlightenment “happiness” rhetoric of the American War of Liberation, most notably purposefully using the English royal address form “Sire” in Posa’s dialogue with Philipp II. In a letter of 21 May 1787, Schiller complains to his publisher Göschen that the editing of *Don Karlos* has resulted in a problem regarding the royal form of address: “Bei Sire ist das e weggestrichen, welches ein Hauptfehler ist denn Sire ohne e heißt bloss Herr im englischen. Sire mit e heißt Ew, Majestät” (NA 24: 97). It is telling that Schiller’s Spanish king bears an English title in a drama begun before the American War of Liberation against England concluded in 1783, a war of political autonomy that simultaneously liberated the new United States from the Church of England, as documented in Thomas Jefferson’s “Virginia Statute on Religious Freedom” (drafted in 1777, enacted in 1786) and the First Amendment of the U.S. Constitution (drafted in 1789, enacted in 1791). In short, the lessons of the liberation of the Netherlands from a church state are most timely in the 1780s, providing a vehicle for art that educates the individual in the contemporary context between the American War of Independence and the French Revolution.

Posa states of his own time: “Das Jahrhundert / ist meinem Ideal nicht reif. Ich lebe / ein Bürger derer, welche kommen werden” (NA 6:185). A moment later, he prophesizes the end of absolutist tyranny and a future cen-

tury of reconciliation between the state and the individual: “Sanftere / Jahrhunderte verdrängen Philips Zeiten; / die bringen mildre Weisheit; Bürgerglück / wird dann versöhnt mit Fürstengröße wandeln, / der karge Staat mit seinen Kindern geitzen, / und die Nothwendigkeit wird menschlich sein” (NA 6:189). Finally, just before his death, in act IV, scene 21, Posa reconciles himself with the possibility of the short-term failure of his vision for the Netherlands, but its realization for millions within centuries: “Er mache — / O, sagen Sie es ihm! das Traumbild wahr, / das kühne Traumbild eines neuen Staates, / der Freundschaft göttliche Geburt. Er lege / die erste Hand an diesen rohen Marmor. / Ob er vollende oder unterliege — / ihm einerlei! Er lege Hand an. Wenn / Jahrhunderte dahin geflohen, wird / die Vorsicht einen Fürstensohn, wie er, / auf einem Thron, wie seiner, wiederholen, / und ihren neuen Liebling mit derselben / Begeisterung entzünden” (NA 6:268-269). Both text internally (European history), as Posa indicates, and text externally (the European present), it is only logical that Schiller’s concern is not late sixteenth-century Spain, but late eighteenth-century humankind: whatever a Philipp does to hinder progress, ideas cannot be stopped, and ideas will lead to actions, as Posa informs Philipp in act III, scene 10: “Sie wollen / allein in ganz Europa — Sich dem Rade / des Weltverhängnisses, das unaufhaltsam / in vollem Laufe rollt, entgegen werfen? / mit Menschenarm in seine Speichen fallen? / Sie warden nicht” (NA 6:190). Progress will come, whether through revolution by the current Karlos or by a future Karlos. As Schiller wrote to Goethe on 27 March 1801: “Aus der Idee aber kann ohne die *That* nichts werden” (NA 29:26). Whether they succeed or fail, the thinker, Schiller, and the doers, Karlos and Posa, begin to chisel this raw stone with a mad vision of individual freedom of, freedom to, and, most importantly, freedom from the subject-external belief systems addressed in Posa’s demand to Philipp II in the name of millions who suffer oppression at the hands of the church state: “Geben Sie Gedankenfreiheit —” (NA 6:191).⁵⁸

Notes

¹ The Royal Confessor Domingo in Schiller’s *Don Karlos*, act IV, scene 15. Friedrich Schiller, *Schillers Werke. Nationalausgabe*. i.A. des Goethe und Schiller-Archivs, des Schiller-Nationalmuseums und der Deutschen Akademie. Julius Petersen et al., eds., (Weimar: Herrmann Böhlau Nachfolger, 1943 ff). Here volume 6:247. Subsequent citations as “NA” with volume and page number(s).

² In his letter to Prince Augustenburg of December 1793, Schiller describes religion’s social function as a temporary patch for an unenlightened populace: “Ich habe hier nicht ohne Absicht Religion und Geschmack in Eine Klasse gesetzt, weil Beide das Verdienst gemein haben, zu einem Surrogat der wahren Tugend zu dienen, und die Gesetzmässigkeit der Handlungen da zu sichern, wo die Pflichtmässigkeit der Gesinnungen nicht zu hoffen ist” (NA 26:330-331).

³ Religion and beauty (“Reize der Schönheit”; NA 21:37) in Schiller’s works have related functions in promoting virtue. Religion results in simulated virtue through coercion, whereas aesthetic education promotes virtue and happiness through the experience of freedom. Both are surrogates for true virtue, not permanent replacements, but temporary aids (NA 26:330-331).

⁴ See Laura Anna Macor, “Die Moralphilosophie des jungen Schiller. Ein ‘Kantianer anti litteram,’” in Jeffrey L. High, Nicholas Martin, and Norbert Oellers, eds., *Who is this Schiller Now?* (Rochester: Camden House, 2011) 99-115. In particular 105-107.

⁵ “Keusch, überirdisch, unkörperlich, heilig, wie seine Religion ist seine dichterische Muse [...] Ich bekenne daher unverhohlen, daß mir für den Kopf desjenigen etwas bange ist, der wirklich und ohne Affektation die-

sen Dichter zu seinem Lieblingsbuche machen kann; [...] auch, dünkte ich, hätte man in Deutschland Früchte genug von seiner gefährlichen Herrschaft gesehen. Nur in gewissen exaltierten Stimmungen des Gemüths kann er gesucht und empfunden werden; deswegen ist er auch der Abgott der Jugend, obgleich bey weitem nicht ihre glücklichste Wahl” (NA: 20:457). See Walter Müller-Seidel on the date of Schiller’s Klopstockian letter to Georg Friedrich Scharffenstein (NA 23: 237).

⁶ See Friederike von Schwerin-High, “Gotthold Ephraim Lessing’s Religious Pluralism in *Nathan the Wise* and The Fragments Controversy,” in: Christopher Nadon, ed., *Enlightenment and Secularism: Essays on the Mobilization of Reason* (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2013) 273-288.

⁷ See Jeffrey L. High, “‘Judex!’ Blasphemy, and Posthumous Conversion: Schiller and (No) Religion,” in: Daniel Purdy, ed., *Yearbook of the Goethe Society of North America* (Rochester: Camden House, 2012) 141-161. Subsequent citations as “High 2012” with page number(s).

⁸ Joseph Gostwick, “Schiller,” in: *German Culture and Christianity. Their Controversy in the Time 1770-1880* (London: F. Norgate, 1882) 318-346; Peter André Alt, *Schiller: Leben, Werk, Zeit. Eine Biographie* (München: Beck, 2004) 264-265; Norbert Oellers, “Schiller und die Religion,” in: *Friedrich Schiller und der Weg in die Moderne*, Walter Hinderer, ed., (Würzburg: Königshausen und Neumann, 2006) 165-186; Manfred Misch, “Schiller und die Religion,” in: Helmut Koopmann, ed., *Schiller-Handbuch*, (Stuttgart: Kröner, 2011) 210-228. Misch provides an extensive bibliography on the subject of Schiller and religion (226-228).

⁹ All of these are addressed in High 2012.

¹⁰ See Alt’s explication of Schiller’s concept of allegory as essentially modern. Peter André Alt, *Begriffsbilder: Studien zur literarischen Allegorie zwischen Opitz und Schiller* (Tübingen: Niemeyer, 1995).

¹¹ Henry Hatfield, *Aesthetic Paganism in German Literature* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1964) 120-121.

¹² See Jeffrey L. High, “The Missions of Moses and Schiller: Monotheism and the Aesthetic Civilization of the Individual,” in: Elisabeth Krimmer and Patricia Simpson, eds., *Religion, Reason, and Culture in the Age of Goethe* (Rochester: Camden House, 2013) 79-98.

¹³ Georg Mueller, “Das Pathos des Gebundenen. Friedrich Schiller als *homo religiosus*,” in: Friedrich Langenfaß, ed., *Zeitwende: Kultur, Kirche, Zeitgeschehen* (26) 1955, 431-459.

¹⁴ Karl Sell, *Die Religion unserer Klassiker: Lessing, Herder, Schiller, Goethe* (Tübingen: Mohr, 1904).

¹⁵ As cited in William Herbert Carruth, “The Religion of Friedrich Schiller,” *PMLA*, volume 19, number 4, (1904): 496-582. Here 498.

¹⁶ Benno von Wiese, “Die Religion Friedrich Schillers,” in *Schiller.reden im Gedenkjahr 1959* (Stuttgart: Klett, 1959) 406-427.

¹⁷ Markus Mynarek, *Spiritualität – Religion – Kirche bei Friedrich Schiller* (Essen: Die Blau Eule, 2012).

¹⁸ Gerhard Fricke, *Der religiöse Sinn der Klassik Schillers: zum Verhältnis von Idealismus und Christentum* (München: Kaiser, 1927).

¹⁹ Walther Rehm, “Schiller und das Barockdrama,” in *Götterstille und Göttertrauer. Aufsätze zur deutsch-antiken Begegnung* (Bern: Francke Verlag, 1951) 62-100. Here 95.

²⁰ Arthur W. McCradle, *Friedrich Schiller and Swabian Pietism*. American University Studies. Series I, Vol. 36 (N.Y.: Lang, 1986). Increasingly, the idea of Schiller’s Swabian Pietism is being criticized as a highly problematic scholarly creation. Istvan Gombocz questions the tradition of speculative studies of religious influence on literature: “es erscheint [...] recht schematisch und tendenziös, das Verhalten von Protagonisten und gleichzeitig Schillers eigene moralphilosophische Orientierung allein auf diese Faktoren zurückzuführen.” Istvan Gombocz, Review of Konrad Meier, *Zerstörungsformen einer verabsolutierten Moral im Frühwerk Friedrich Schillers*, in: *Jahrbuch für internationale Germanistik*, Jahrgang XXVI, Heft 2 (Bern: Peter Lang, 1994) 119-121. Here 120. Most recently, Ulrich Ott appears to have put an end to the speculation in: Ulrich Ott, “Schiller und der Pietismus,” in: Wilfried Barner, Christine Lubkoll, Ernst Osterkamp, and Ulrich Raulff, eds., *Jahrbuch der Deutschen Schiller-Gesellschaft* (Göttingen: Wallstein, 2011) 189-214.

²¹ Peter Meinhold, “Schillers spiritualistische Religionsphilosophie und Geschichtskritik,” in *Zeitschrift für Religions- und Geistesgeschichte*, vol. 8, no. 2 (1956): 218-241. Here 240.

²² Adolf Schmitthenner, “Schillers Stellung zur Religion,” in: *Protestantische Monatshefte* (1905) 281-296. Here 296. See here the title of a work by Johannes Kaiser that I have not been able to locate: “Die beiden Hauptzüge der religiös-sittlichen Weltanschauung Schillers.”

²³ Susanna Rubinstein, “Schillers Stellung zur Religion,” *Pädagogisches Magazin*, Heft 275 (Langensalza: Beyer & Söhne, 1906) 5.

²⁴ Hans-Jürgen Benedict, "Vertrau auf Gott und rette den Bedrängten: Theologische Annäherung an Friedrich Schiller," in *Glaubenssachen*: NDR Kultur, 13 December 2009;3.

²⁵ In "Die Sendung Moses" (1790), Schiller uses the term "Vernunftreligion" not to describe his own philosophy, but to describe Moses' religion of philosophical truth packaged in the fantastic, created for a people and a time Moses considered unprepared for the rule of reason (NA 17:392). Peter-André Alt demonstrates Schiller's rejection of "protestantischen Purismus einer aufgeklärten Vernunftreligion" and the impossibility of a mythopoetic restoration of ancient unity in modernity. Peter André Alt, *Schiller: Leben, Werk, Zeit. Eine Biographie* (München: Beck, 2004) 264-265.

²⁶ In short, the inevitable result of state religious reform is merely a variation of the initial constitutional failure, namely, continued explicit coercion to practice a (reformed version of the same) state religion.

²⁷ Though a more comprehensive study would include a discussion of the important tolerance discourses of e.g., Spinoza, Hobbes, Bacon, John Locke, Pierre Bayle in particular, Montesquieu, Diderot, Lessing, and Hume among others, the narrow focus here is the relation of Schiller's concept of virtue and the freedom from religion discourses in his works, in particular, in *Don Karlos*.

²⁸ "From Edinburgh to Williamsburg to Ludwigsburg: The Influence of the Scottish Enlightenment on Thomas Jefferson and Friedrich Schiller," in: Peter Pabisch, ed., *Jahrbuch für internationale Germanistik* (Bern: Peter Lang, 2005) 281-313.

²⁹ Larry P. Aarn, ed., *The US Constitution: A Reader* (Hillsdale, MI: Hillsdale College Press, 2012) 117.

³⁰ Julian P. Boyd et al., eds., *The Papers of Thomas Jefferson*, (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1950) vol. 1, page 429. Subsequently cited as "Boyd" with volume and page number.

³¹ Letter to Roger C. Weightman of 24 June 1826, in: Jean M. Yarbrough, *The Essential Jefferson* (Indianapolis/Cambridge: Hackett Publishing, 2006) 277.

³² "Virginia Statute on Religious Freedom," in: Vincent Phillip Muñoz, *God and the Founders: Madison, Washington, and Jefferson* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009) 92.

³³ Neil H. Cogan, ed., *The Complete Bill of Rights. The Drafts, Debates, Sources, and Origins* (Oxford and New York: Oxford University Press, 1997) 11.

³⁴ H. A. Washington, ed., *The Writings of Thomas Jefferson* (New York: Derby & Jackson, 1859) 8.

³⁵ "The Declaration of the Rights of Man and of Citizens," in: James Harvey Robinson, ed., *Translations and Reprints from the Original Sources of European History* (New York: Henry Holt & Co., 1901) 7.

³⁶ Maximilian Robespierre, "The Festival of the Supreme Being," in: Lewis Copeland, Lawrence W. Lamm, and Stephen J. McKenna, eds., *Great Speeches: 292 Speeches from Pericles to Nelson Mandela* (Mineola, NY: Dover, 1999), 83-85.

³⁷ In the strictly monitored religious confines of the Karlsschule, Schiller established the inscrutable practice of mixing philosophical with mythological and religious metaphors, and expressing modern experience in ancient metaphor. This is evident from the earliest poems written at the Karlsschule — "Der Abend" (1776), "Der Eroberer" (1776) — to the last — "Elisium" (1780 or 1781) and "Gruppe aus dem Tartarus" (1780 or 1781), and continues in his mature poetry. Calvin Thomas notes the "free blending of Christian with pagan conceptions." Calvin Thomas, *The Life and Works of Friedrich Schiller* (New York: Holt, 1906) 67-68. For centuries, critics have confused Schiller's metaphorical expression of the inexpressible with a genuine expression of religious conviction, though they provide no evidence why anyone might agree with them, aside from the fact that metaphors can be vague. As in the First Virtue Essay, Schiller's more spiritual outbursts are routinely accompanied by heretical or blasphemous ideas. For a sampling of positions on Schiller and religion, see High, "Schiller and (No) Religion," 144.

³⁸ There are perhaps as many as three clear allusions to the New Testament, all of which, significantly, refer to the Sermon on the Mount, where Christ appears more than elsewhere as a human teaching humans. Here Christ admonishes — in terms of separation of church and state, and in close agreement with Schiller's thesis regarding ulterior motives — that since hypocrites worship in public, personal religious beliefs are best kept private. Schiller is not alone in singling out the Sermon on the Mount: "Deists like Jefferson and Franklin went so far as to believe that the only thing worth keeping of the Christian faith was the Sermon on the Mount." Gordon S. Wood, *The Radicalism of the American Revolution* (New York: Knopf, 1992) 158.

³⁹ For Schiller's references to Socrates, see Jeffrey L. High, "'Gehört allzuviel Güte, Leutseeligkeit und grosse Freygebigkeit im engsten Verstande zur Tugend?': Schiller, Socrates, and Secular Jesus," in: *Reading*

Schiller, Special Issue of *Philosophical Readings*, Laura Anna Macor, ed. (2013) 7-49.

⁴⁰ Cf. Psalms 1:4: "The ungodly are not so: but are like the chaff which the wind driveth away." Ironically, however, Socrates appears in the role of the godly, and it is the heavens that will be blown away.

⁴¹ See the representative entry on "An die Freude" in the *Schiller-Handbuch*, which reduces the in so many senses of the word revolutionary poem to "keineswegs revolutionär." In a single paragraph here, Schiller's metaphor for optimism becomes a concrete invocation of the Christian concept of heaven, a transformation that ignores the obvious implications for Christianity of a poem that explicitly deletes the concept of Hell and whose God is Zeus/Jupiter. Georg-Michael Schulz, "An die Freude," in: Mathias Luserke-Jaqui, ed., *Schiller-Handbuch. Leben – Werk – Wirkung* (Stuttgart: Metzler, 2005) 259-261. As Schiller wrote in 1795, "Furcht ist der Geist aller Gottesverehrung" (NA 26:317), ergo, remove the fear, and "Religion ist dem größern Theile der Menschen nichts mehr, wenn wir ihre Gemälde von Himmel und Hölle zernichten — und doch sind des nur Gemälde der Phantasie, Räthsel ohne Auflösung, Schreckbilder und Lockungen aus der Ferne" ("Die Schaubühne als moralische Anstalt"; NA 20:91).

⁴² A more in depth version of this argument appears in Jeffrey L. High, "Schiller, Freude, Kleist und Rache / On the German Freedom Ode," in: Dieter Sevin and Christoph Zeller, eds., *Heinrich von Kleist – Style and Concept: Explorations in Literary Dissonance* (Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2013) 123-145. Here 130-135.

⁴³ Dieter Hildebrandt, *Die Neunte. Schiller, Beethoven und die Geschichte eines musikalischen Weitererfolgs* (Munich: Deutscher Taschenbuch Verlag, 2009) 99-101.

⁴⁴ In the philosophical dialogue, *Philosophische Briefe* (1786), Schiller's Julius declares, "Du hast mir den Glauben gestohlen, der mir Frieden gab," and glumly describes his insight that the "mächtiges Wunderwerk der Religion" lies in the empty promise of the afterlife and its desperate acceptance by the dying. Raphael further seeks to disprove Julius' contention that Christianity is of divine origin by demonstrating that every other pre- and post-Christian religion demonstrates the same concerns and offers only some alternative strategies, leading Julius to conclude: "Wozu brauche ich einen Gott, wenn ich ohne den Schöpfer ausreiche?" (NA 20:110).

⁴⁵ "Die Lügnerin, gedungen von Despoten, / Hat für die Wahrheit Schatten dir geboten, / Du bist nicht mehr, wenn dieser Schein verfällt" (NA 1:167).

⁴⁶ "Du hast gehofft, dein Lohn ist abgetragen, / Dein Glaube war dein zugewognes Glück. / Du konntest deine Weisen fragen, / Was man von der Minute ausgeschlagen, / Gibt keine Ewigkeit zurück" (NA 1:169).

⁴⁷ "Zu Rapps Kritik der Resignation" (NA 22:178).

⁴⁸ What does live on, lives on in history and art, as described in the poems "The Gods of Ancient Greece" (1788) and "Nänie" (1800).

⁴⁹ The familiar Schillerian alternative implied is human and humane justice that respects individual religious, political, and artistic freedom of thought and expression (Gedankenfreiheit), and secures freedom from "compulsory unification of opinion." "Compulsory unification of opinion" was the phrase used by Supreme Court Justice Robert Jackson to declare the coerced recitation of the "Pledge of Allegiance" unconstitutional in "West Virginia State Board of Education v. Barnette" in 1943: "Those who begin coercive elimination of dissent soon find themselves eliminating dissenters. Compulsory unification of opinion achieves only the unanimity of the graveyard." James W. Fraser, *Between Church and State: Religion & Public Education in a Multicultural America* (New York: St. Martin's Press, 1999) 136. Note the similarity to Marquis Posa's Rousseauian description of Spanish civilization in Schiller's *Don Karlos* (1787) as "die Ruhe eines Kirchhofs" (NA 6:190).

⁵⁰ Responding to the charges of blasphemy in a letter to Körner just after the publication of "Die Götter Griechenlandes" in 1788, Schiller distinguished between the concept of God discussed by philosophers, the "dream vision" worshipped by the mob, and his own clearly metaphorical "miscarriage" in the invocation of deities: "Der Gott den ich in den Göttern Griechenlands in Schatten stelle ist nicht der Gott der Philosophen, oder auch nur das wohlthätige Traumbild des grossen Haufens, sondern es ist eine aus vielen gebrechlichen schiefen Vorstellungsarten zusammen gefloßene Mißgeburt" (NA 25:167). See Jeffrey L. High, "Friedrich Schiller, Secular Virtue, and The Gods of Ancient Greece (1788)," in Christopher Nadon, ed., *Enlightenment and Secularism: Essays on the Mobilization of Reason* (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2013) 315-324.

⁵¹ Novalis cites the source of uproar as a reaction to perceived atheism: "Man hat fast überall über das vortreffliche Gedicht des Herrn Raths Schiller 'Die Götter Griechenlands' Weh u[nd] Ach geschrien, ihm für einen Atheisten und ich weiß nicht für alles erklärt und voll heiligen

Eifers inh geradezu der Hölle übergeben." Novalis, "Apologie von Friedrich Schiller" in: Paul Kluckhohn and Richard Samuel, eds., *Novalis, Werke* (Stuttgart: Kohlhammer, 1960/1981) 18-20. Here 24. Subsequent citations as "Novalis" with page number(s).

⁵² In Schiller's journal *Thalia* in March 1789, Christian Gottfried Körner published a defense of Schiller and his poem, "Ueber die Freiheit des Dichters bei der Wahl seiner Stoffe." In March 1788 in the *Teutscher Merkur*, Karl Ludwig von Knebel anonymously published a moralizing Christian attack against Schiller's Polytheism (NA 25:56, 485). In the August 1789 edition of *Teutscher Merkur*, Franz Kleist published a response poem entitled "Das Lob des einzigen Gottes / ein Gegenstück zu den Göttern Griechenlands" (NA 25:661).

⁵³ "Nennt der meinige sich dem Verstande? / Birgt ihn etwa der Gewölke Zelt? Mühsam späht ich im Ideenlande, / Fruchtlos in der Sinnenwelt," (NA 1:192). The 13th strophe is arguably more blasphemous: "Wohin tret' ich? Diese traur'ge Stille, / Kündigt sie mir meinen Schöpfer an? / Finster, wie er selbst, ist seine Hülle, / Mein Entsagen—was ihn feiern kann" (NA 1:193).

⁵⁴ The guilty party here, according to Forster, is Stolberg, the "enemy of mankind, who attached piety and damnation" to an artistic vision. Georg Forster, "Fragment eines Briefes an einen deutschen Schriftsteller über Schillers Götter Griechenlands" in Gerhard Steiner, ed., *Georg Forster, Philosophische Schriften* (Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, 1958) 53-70. Here 68.

⁵⁵ Novalis, "Kann ein Atheist auch moralisch tugendhaft aus Grundsätzen seyn?" (Novalis 20).

⁵⁶ Heinrich Heine, "Die Romantische Schule," in: Fritz Strich, ed., *Heinrich Heine, Sämtliche Werke*, vol. 4 (München: Georg Müller, 1925) 246-429. Here 296.

⁵⁷ "Ich werde immer eine schlechte Quelle für einen künftigen Geschichtsforscher sein, der das Unglück hat, sich an mich zu wenden. Aber ich werde vielleicht auf Unkosten der historischen Wahrheit Leser und Hörer finden und hie und da mit jener ersten, philosophischen Zusammentreffen." Letter to Caroline von Beulwitz of 10 December 1788 (NA 25:154). See also *Ueber das Pathetische*: "Noch mehr wird man sich davon überzeugen, [...] wie wenig die poetische Kraft des Eindrucks, den sittliche Charaktere oder Handlungen auf uns machen, von ihrer historischen Realität abhängt. Unser Wohlgefallen an idealischen Charakteren verliert nicht durch die Erinnerung, daß sie poetische Fiktionen sind, denn es ist die *poetische*, nicht die historische Wahrheit, auf welche alle ästhetische Wirkung sich gründet. Die poetische Wahrheit besteht aber nicht darinn, daß etwas wirklich geschehen ist, sondern darinn, daß es geschehen konnte [...]" (NA 20. 218).

⁵⁸ I would like to express my sincere thanks to Elizabeth Chan, Elaine Chen, Madeline Foss, Natalie Martz, Alexandra Petrus, Chelsea Powell, and Emily Wysocki (all at California State University, Long Beach), to Adan Gallardo (Pomona College), to Sophia Clark, Curtis Maughan, and Adam Merki (all at Vanderbilt), to Prissilla Sanchez (University of Oregon), and to Rebecca Stewart (Harvard) for their support in researching this study and preparing the manuscript.